

SEMINA MUNDI

**Seeding the EcoSomatic Community in Italy
First Generative Gathering**

CasaNave Alle Mura – Tuscania (Viterbo) 21–22 March 2026

Call and Background: www.raffaelerufo.com/ecosomatics/semina-mundi

Semina Mundi is a project conceived and coordinated by Raffaele Rufo (PhD). The gathering is organised by Kinesfera APS.

Organising group: Raffaele Rufo, Gloria Desideri, Marco Adda, Silvia Luraschi, Cinzia Delorenzi, Roberta Goeta, Signa Schiavo Campo, Valeria Carovana, Lorenzo Bazzurro, Diana Tedoldi

PARTICIPATORY PROGRAMME

DAY 1 – SATURDAY 21/3

Recognising Ourselves as a Community of Practices

09:00 – 10:00

Arrival and Activation of the Participants Map

Locations: CasaNave Garden and Terrace (Relax Room in case of rain)

Facilitation: Organising team

Participants arrive informally between the garden and terrace, with registration and collection of contributions, including the shared dinner fee. At the same time, an initial embodied mapping of the network is activated: participants position themselves on a large paper roll (“Mycelium”), indicating origins, territories, and fields of practice. Desires and proposals for the late-afternoon open space are also collected on the paper board — what I wish to offer / what I wish to receive — together with preferences for the ecosomatic workshops taking place in the early afternoon.

10:00 – 10:15

Welcome and Opening Ritual – Breathing with the Place

Location: CasaNave Terrace (or Main Hall in case of rain)

Facilitation: Organising team

We gather together to mark the beginning of the journey, moving from individual arrival into a shared presence: the welcome introduces the meaning of the gathering and the facilitation team, while attention gradually turns towards the place hosting us. Through a brief activation, we enter into a relationship with the genius loci of Tuscania — what we perceived upon arriving and what the place itself suggests — using breath as the first collective gesture for attuning with one another and with the environment.

10:15 – 10:45

Activating the Spaces of CasaNave and the Small Groups

Locations: Terrace, Main Hall, Garden

Facilitation: Organising team

Participants, divided into groups of 5–6 people, each accompanied by a member of the organising team, begin a fluid journey through the spaces of CasaNave — terrace, main hall, and garden — gradually encountering and inhabiting them. During this movement, the facilitator supports introductions among participants and explains how the spaces can be used, while each person is invited to share who they are, what they bring, and what they sense within the place, through open and adaptable modes of exchange.

10:45 – 11:45

Embodied Plenary – Recognising Ourselves as One Group

Location: Main Hall

Facilitation: Gloria Desideri, Raffaele Rufo, participants

The group gathers in the hall to progressively enter a shared dimension through the body: the session begins with somatic listening and cellular breathing, moving towards relational attunement, and continues with embodied circle games and the exchange of names, activating rhythm, attention, and energy. The plenary then opens into a practice of gifting: participants are invited to offer brief fragments of their own practice (maximum 3 minutes), which become shared experiences through listening, imitation, and resonance.

11:45 – 12:15

Break

Locations: Relax Room, Terrace, Garden

Break with coffee, tea, biscuits, and fruit. The refreshment table is set up in the Relax Room, while the terrace and garden remain available for resting, meeting, and informal conversations.

12:15 – 13:15

Listening to Territories: Emerging Needs

Location: Main Hall

Facilitation: Raffaele Rufo, Valeria Carovana

12:15 – 12:30

How Semina Mundi Emerges – Memories of Encounters and Voices of Practitioners

Through a brief evocative moment connected with the La Selva residency (2023), Semina Mundi is introduced as a process emerging from situated encounters and the real needs of practitioners and territories: the burnt forest of the Mediterranean bush in Ostia becomes an image and threshold for this work, a wounded field from which the need for listening, relationship, and transformation takes shape. From this starting point, an experiential invitation activates collective memory, connecting the present gathering with the Genius Loci symposium (September 2025) and the “Seeding Communities” questionnaires (November 2025), which highlighted the widespread need to map ecosomatic practices in Italy and create networks.

12:30 – 13:10

Poetic Constellations of Needs – Collective Emergence and Composition

A three-phase process intertwining emergence, relationship, and composition:

Phase 1 – Individual Emergence

Each participant writes words on A4 sheets responding to the question: “What is a need of the territory-community in which I live or work?”

Each A4 sheet contains only one word. The words are hung up on the thin rope crossing the space. Then the group picks words and place them on the floor forming initial visual “islands.” The group observes and may move the sheets to create constellations of meaning.

Phase 2 – Haiku Composition

In pairs, trios, or small groups, participants choose some of the words that have emerged and combine them without rewriting them, composing Haiku as micro-constellations of needs. The work unfolds through relationship, intuition, and listening, allowing connections between territories and lived experiences to emerge.

Phase 3 – Embodied Sharing

The Haiku are placed in the space and observed as a collective landscape. Each group shares its Haiku through voice, body, and presence, making the field of needs visible and shareable.

13:10 – 13:15

Closing and Orientation

Brief closing with reminders about the next moments of the day and transition towards lunch.

13:15 – 14:30

Lunch

14:30 – 15:30

Meditative and Performative Walk Through the Historical Village of Tuscania

Location: From CasaNave to the Torre di Lavello Park

Facilitation: Marco Adda

The group moves together on foot through the historic centre of Tuscania, from the walls of the town to the Torre di Lavello Park. The walk has a light, meditative, and performative quality: a crossing of urban spaces through listening to the place, the group, and the relationships emerging along the way. Each participant is invited to listen and discover their own resonance with the environment, allowing spontaneous interactions and a gradual reconciliation with the place to unfold. We leave together and arrive together.

15:30 – 15:45

Formation of Self-Organised Practice Exchange Groups

Location: Small Arena – Torre di Lavello Park

Facilitation: Raffaele Rufo

Starting from the desires and proposals collected during the morning on the paper board, affinities and shared interests are facilitated in order to form the afternoon practice exchange groups. Through the meeting between what each participant wishes to offer and receive, co-facilitated groups emerge, autonomously defining the format, size, and location of their activities. Groups may vary in scale — small, large, even pairs or trios — and choose where to carry out their practices among the CasaNave spaces (main hall, relax room, terrace, garden) or external locations in agreement with the wider group.

15:45 – 16:00

Break

(For participants joining the workshop with Roberta Goeta and Signa Schiavo Campo, this is the moment to return to CasaNave.)

16:00 – 17:30

Ecosomatic Workshops

Workshop 1 – Future Ancestors

Location: CasaNave Main Hall

Facilitation: Roberta Goeta, Signa Schiavo Campo

Is it possible to face the contemporary poly-crisis by transforming our relationship with time? This eco-poetic workshop proposes embodied imaginative practices for exploring the body-mind as a meeting point between past and future, in relationship with our ancestors (human and more-than-human) and descendants. Through a somatic journey in time, participants orient themselves towards broader temporalities — geological, biological, and symbolic — in order to imagine possible futures and forms of coexistence that recognise continuity between past, present, and future.

Practices: imaginal listening, micro-movement, eco-poetic writing.

Workshop 2 – We Within the Living Fabrics of the Landscape

Location: Torre di Lavello Park and surroundings

Facilitation: Cinzia Delorenzi

What happens when the body ceases to be a boundary and becomes a threshold? This outdoor workshop explores the landscape as a living fabric, a web of relationships of which we are part. Through practices of listening, movement, and perception, the body becomes a porous and sensitive field, expanding relationships with oneself, with others, and with the more-than-human. The work develops through micro-movement, perceptive walking, gaze, and touch, opening possibilities for shared forms of presence in which the individual body extends into an emergent “We.”

Practices: movement from micro to macro, sensory orientation within the landscape, relationship through gaze and touch, brief compositional explorations and sharings.

17:30 – 19:30

Open Space – Self-Organised Practice Exchange

Locations: CasaNave (Main Hall, Relax Room, Terrace, Garden), Torre di Lavello Park, Umberto II Park, and other outdoor spaces

Facilitation: Self-organised by participants

An open self-organised space unfolds in which the groups formed during the afternoon freely activate exchanges of practices, choosing times, places, and modalities. Proposals emerge from shared desires and resonances, generating experiences distributed between indoor and outdoor spaces. Participation is optional: a space for exploration, encounter, and co-facilitation, where practices emerge in spontaneous and situated ways.

19:30

Collective Dinner (Optional)

Location: CasaNave

For those who wish, a shared catered dinner (contribution: €8). An informal moment for continuing exchange and conviviality.

21:00

Creative Jam – Open Practice and Performative Space

Location: CasaNave Main Hall

A collective space for free expression in which multiple forms may emerge: live music, singing, performative actions, poetic readings, short theatre pieces, presentations of fragments of work. Participants are invited to bring their own musical instruments. Piano, mixer, and sound system

will be available. A large paper roll will also be present as a space for open graphic expression, potentially becoming part of the documentation of the gathering.

DAY 2 – SUNDAY 22/3

Integrating Perceptions, Seeding Ideas and Intentions

08:00 – 09:00

Open Space – Bodywork, Awakening and Orientation

Locations: Main Hall, Relax Room, Garden, and CasaNave Terrace

Facilitation: Organising team and participants

The morning opens with a free space dedicated to bodywork and embodied awakening in the Main Hall, while coffee and tea are available in the Relax Room. This is also a moment for orienting within the day: preferences for the thematic working tables are confirmed and desires and proposals for the seeding of practices are collected.

09:00 – 09:30

Somatic Tuning – Listening and Grounding

Location: CasaNave Main Hall

Facilitation: Gloria Desideri

A time for somatic listening and cellular breathing to ground and arrive together, entering into a deeper relationship with oneself, the group, and the space.

09:30 – 11:00

Thematic Working Tables – Applications and Sustainability of Ecosomatic Practices

Locations: Relax Room, Terrace, Main Hall, Garden

Facilitation: Organising team (at least one organising member present at each table)

Participants distribute themselves among thematic tables in small groups (maximum 8 people) in order to maintain an immersive and participatory quality. Groups form according to the areas of interest that have emerged, articulating themselves into more specific subgroups. Each table is an active co-facilitated space in which roles are shared: keeping time, supporting the flow of exchange, collecting ideas, and preparing a sharing for the final forum. The work begins from

the territorial needs that emerged the previous day, relating them to possible concrete applications of ecosomatic practices.

Main areas of work include:

- Education and training (adults, youth, schools, childhood)
- Arts and culture (performance, publications, events)
- Health and wellbeing (holistic practices, healthcare contexts)

Guiding questions:

- What is a real and concrete need?
- How does territorial regeneration orient approaches, practices, and possibilities for intervention?
- What kind of intervention format can be imagined?
- Who could become partners?
- What is a micro-step that could realistically be implemented within the next 6 months (2026)?

Sharing: Each group prepares a synthesis to be shared during the final forum, freely choosing the format: map, poster, performative action, embodied storytelling, diagram, or proposal prototype.

11:00 – 11:30

Break

11:30 – 13:00

Seeding Ideas, Seedlings, and Practices

Locations: Garden, Terrace, CasaNave Main Hall, and outdoor spaces

Mode: Free participation, co-facilitated activity

This phase intertwines concrete action and collective reflection, creating a bridge between ecology and community. The group freely distributes itself among three interconnected areas:

- Seeding seedlings: reactivating the garden beds of CasaNave through working the soil and planting seedlings, as a real gesture of care and continuity.
- Seeding ideas: open conversations and exchanges among participants, allowing intuitions, connections, and future possibilities to emerge.
- Seeding practices: a second moment in which participants are invited to activate exchanges of practices starting from desires and proposals collected during the morning.

The space remains fluid and traversable: some people work with the soil, others engage in dialogue, while others activate practices, moving between different dimensions. Participants are invited to connect these three moments, combining concrete gestures, words, and practices — for example, linking the planting of seedlings with the emergence of shared intentions or visions.

13:00 – 14:00

Final Forum – From Dialogue to Next Steps

Location: Main Hall

Facilitation: Raffaele Rufo

The group gathers in plenary to collect and relaunch what has emerged during the two days. The participant map — the “Mycelium” — is reactivated together with the materials produced: territorial needs, workshop sharings, and traces from the open spaces and seedings. The thematic working tables share a synthesis of their work (maximum 5 minutes per group), also through creative forms, presenting visions, proposals, and first operational directions.

From these emergences, a collective space opens to outline the next steps of the network (6–12 months): possible collaborations, future gatherings, and shared projects. The Genius Loci 2026 symposium (18–20 September, Spazio Rossellini) is announced, including the addition of a third training day as a first testing ground for the network. The activation of an online Google Drive with a Creative Commons licence is also proposed in order to collect and share the documentation generated by Semina Mundi. An online harvesting and sharing meeting is agreed upon in order to give continuity and form to the generated content.

The journey concludes with a brief embodied ritual to integrate the experience and mark the transition.